

IDENTIFYING AND DEVELOPING INDIVIDUAL CAPABILITIES DURING THE STUDENT PERIOD

Tulyaganova Gulnoza Olimjon kizi

PhD, Senior teacher of the Department of "Social Sciences, Pedagogy and Psychology" of the
Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute

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Abstract. *The article discusses the problem of increasing the educational activity of students of institutions, taking into account age and psychological-pedagogical characteristics.*

Keywords: *student, age characteristics, cognitive activity, activation.*

Student age is a phenomenon directly related to the development of a higher educational institution. K.D.Ushinsky called this age "the most decisive", because it is this period that determines the future of a person, it is a very active period of intensive work on oneself.

L.D.Stolyarenko describes the student community as a special social category of people, a special community organized by a higher education institution [1]. According to the definition of I.A.Zimnaya, students include people who purposefully, systematically acquire knowledge and professional skills, characterized by the highest level of education, the most active consumption of culture and a high level of cognitive motivation [2]. According to B.G.Ananiev, the life period from 17 to 25 years is important as the final stage of personality formation and the main stage of professionalization. According to B.G.Ananiev, by the age of 17, a person creates optimal subjective conditions for the formation of self-education activity skills [3].

A modern student of the institute is, first of all, a young man who has all the opportunities for further development. The first-year student, who is the most important intellectual potential of the society, is yesterday's student, he does not have the necessary experience and urgently needs to acquire it.

In this regard, it is very important for the teacher to direct the activity of the first-year student to adapt to independent work as soon as possible. This implies the development of cognitive activity. It is necessary to explain to the student that he carries out this activity not only to successfully pass exams, but also to acquire knowledge, skills and abilities.

Student's age

The student has general age characteristics: biological (high type of nervous activity, unconditioned reflexes, instincts, physical strength, etc.); psychological (unity of psychological processes, states and characteristics); social (social relations, qualities, belonging to a certain social group, etc.). At the same time, when studying a particular student, it is necessary to take into account the individual characteristics of each one, the characteristics of his mental processes and situations.

It is very important for us to know the characteristics of the transition from adolescence to adolescence. At this age, people try to find their place in society, seek to understand themselves, and have a critical attitude not only to themselves, but also to others. These features are distinguished by domestic and foreign researchers-A.G.Asmolov, L.S.Vygotsky, A.N.Leontiev, D.I.Feldstein and others.

Student years are a special stage of life. The basis is very clear - training in accordance with the goal, tasks and, most importantly, the motivation that arises as a result of obtaining a specialty at this institution.

This is especially difficult for first-year students. The time between finishing school and starting to study at the institute is very short, and it is necessary to significantly change the previously set goals, deeply revise your habits and behavior, as a result, new qualities that contribute to the performance of new social roles will be, manifestation of personal qualities such as independence, curiosity, initiative. The student faces difficulties related to the need to get used to new things - classmates, teachers of specialized subjects, different forms of reporting and importance in the eyes of others.

There is a complex dynamic relationship between the learning process and development that changes with age. L. S.Vygotsky [4] proved that developmental processes do not coincide with educational processes, but follow them. He defined the "zone" of proximal development, characterized by the range of tasks that the student can solve not independently, but under the guidance of the teacher, at a certain stage of development. But over time, with the development of cognitive abilities, these tasks are performed independently by him.

Researchers identify sensitive periods of human ontogeny that are most favorable for the development of abilities. During these periods, particularly intensive development of abilities may occur before the general development of the individual. This is an important condition for the formation of abilities.

Moments of social adjustment

Components of this structure: increasing the functional level of various mechanisms of activity, stabilizing these levels and reducing them. As a result of the experiment B.G.Ananov, compared the moments that make up the structure of the development of psychophysiological functions of a person, divided the years of life, which include the moments of increase, stabilization and decrease of the functional level (table 1).

Table 1

Moments of development and their different micro maturity period ratio

Microperiods, years	Increase the functional level %	Stabilization,%	Functional Degradation %
18-22	46,8	20,6	32,6
23-27	44,0	19,8	36,2
28-32	46,2	15,8	38,0
33-35	11,2	33,3	55,5

Analysis of table data shows that 18 to 22 years old (the age that interests us the most) has the largest percentage (46.8%) of the functional level, i.e. the greatest increase in cognitive abilities.

College age is characterized by indicators: stable attention, developed imagination, greater integration of memory. During this period, personality and behavior style are developing rapidly. It's no secret that most students set themselves "big" tasks. In this regard, the problem of self-

education and self-education is in the first place. Therefore, when organizing any activity of a student, it is necessary to take into account his psychology, which changes with each new course. During the student period, important changes occur in interpersonal relationships. They are distinguished by their inclination to more personal and meaningful interaction, high reflectivity, and become a source of emotional experiences. At this age, the need to build understanding and sympathy, empathy, and trusting relationships increases. Communication with peers is of particular importance and becomes one of the leading factors of personal development.

V.S.Ilyin [5] va V.A.Nikitin [6] *determines the effectiveness of educational processes and the restoration of moral and mental health depends on how quickly the student adapts to new living conditions*. Adaptation in educational activities is related to mastering cognitive methods and orientation to cognitive values. The change in the familiar environment can be aggravated by dissatisfaction with the results of studies, interpersonal relations, the loss of a familiar status in the group, anxiety in choosing a future profession. It's stressful and frustrating leading to fatigue, exhaustion and poor performance. Maladaptation can be manifested in a change in the internal regulation system, a serious deviation in the psyche, self-destructive behavior, aggression.

For some students, the development of a new behavioral stereotype is abrupt, and for others, it is more or less smooth. Undoubtedly, the characteristics of this reconstruction are related to the characteristics of higher nervous activity. However, social factors are very important here. Knowing the individual characteristics of the student, building a system of introducing him to new types of activities and a new social circle on the basis of it, it makes it possible to avoid the syndrome of incorrect adaptation, to make the process of adaptation smooth and psychologically comfortable.

Social adaptation in the institute is divided into the following. Professional adaptation is understood as adaptation to the nature, content, conditions and organization of the educational process, development of independence skills in educational work; socio-psychological adaptation - adaptation of a person to a group, with it establishing relationships, developing a unique style of behavior.

Many first-year students face great difficulties at first due to a lack of independent study skills. They do not know how to write lectures, work with textbooks, learn from primary sources, analyze large amounts of data, express their thoughts clearly and precisely.

Adaptation of students to the educational process usually ends at the end of the 2nd semester and the beginning of the 3rd semester.

Types and groups of students

Many researchers in the field of psychology and pedagogy found that some students work hard and willingly to master new knowledge. The difficulties that arise at the same time only add to them energy and the desire to achieve the goal. Others everything they do "under the stick" and the obstacles drastically reduce their activity.

Teachers and psychologists explain this with the individual psychological characteristics of students. Such characteristics include intelligence (the ability to acquire new knowledge), creativity (the ability to independently develop new knowledge), high self-esteem, and others.

Three types of students are distinguished according to the nature of the educational activity and the behavioral models corresponding to it.

It goes beyond the knowledge defined by the curriculum and science programs of the First Kind of Cognitive Interests. Students are active in all areas of the institute's life and are focused on wide specialization and versatile professional training.

Students assigned to the second type are distinguished by their clear focus on specialization. Here too, cognitive activity goes beyond the curriculum, but not wider, but deeper. The entire activity system is limited to the scope of "close professional interests".

And finally, the cognitive activity of the third type of students is strictly aimed at mastering knowledge and skills within the framework of the curriculum. This type exhibits a minimum level of activity and creativity.

Different people come to the Institute with different Attitudes and different "starting conditions". In this regard, it is interesting to analyze student youth in relation to their chosen professions. The student body is divided into three groups.

The first group is students focused on education as a profession. This group has the largest number of students who are interested in future work, and the desire for self-realization is the most important. Only they tend to continue their education. All other factors are not so important for them. *The second group* consists of business-oriented students. Their attitude to education is completely different: education serves as a tool (or a possible initial stage) to try to create your own business, trade, etc. in the future. they understand that this field requires education over time, but they are less interested in their profession than the representatives of the first group. *The third group—students*, who can be called "uncertain" on the one hand, and on the other hand—are overwhelmed by various problems of personal, daily planning. They face daily, personal, housing, family problems. It can be said that this is a "go with the flow" group. They cannot choose their own path, for them education and profession are not interests that characterize other groups. It is possible that the self-determination of this group of students will occur later, but for now we assume that this group includes people whose process of self-determination, path selection and purposefulness is atypical.

Choose profession, the process of studying at the institute today has become a pragmatic, purposeful business for many people that is in line with the changes in the modern world. The importance of education as a social phenomenon receded into the background. With the advent of "Commercial" recruitment, wealthy students who are not used to denying themselves anything, are sure of the correctness of their choices, and are well aware of the specifics of future professional activity, came to the institute. Inspired by the example of their parents (usually entrepreneurs), these students look to the future without fear: for them, it is a clear prospect. At the same time, in general, students' behavior is characterized by a high level of conformity.

Different courses solve different problems during studies at the institute. In the first year, there are tasks to familiarize the former applicant with the student forms of collective life: the first-year student does not have a differentiated approach to his roles. The second year is the period of the students' most intense academic activity. All forms of education are intensively included in the life of second-year students. Students receive general education; their broad cultural requirements and needs are formed. The process of adapting to a specific environment is largely complete. The beginning of the third course-specialization, increasing interest in scientific work as a reflection of the further development and deepening of professional interests of students. The urgent need for specialization (forms of personality formation in the institute are determined by the specialization factor in the main characteristics) often leads to a narrowing of the field of

multifaceted interests of the individual. The prospect of finishing the fourth course-the institute soon-forms concrete practical attitudes to the type of future activity. New, increasingly relevant values related to financial and family status, workplace, etc. will appear. Students are gradually moving away from the collective life forms of the institute.

The aesthetic aspect is of great importance for the student's educational activity, it gives a certain direction to this activity, contributes to the development of interests. Cognitive activity, curiosity and aesthetic education are inextricably linked. The aesthetic content of cognitive activity is somewhat weakened under the pressure of various social structures and interests.

The effectiveness of cognitive activity can be ensured by certain pedagogical conditions, through which we understand a set of interrelated measures in the educational process, which ensures the readiness of students to engage in creative communication with information.

Uniqueness in relationships The technical institute has its own characteristics due to the uniqueness of the goals, tasks, content, forms and methods of the educational process, as well as the age and psychological characteristics of the students.

Socio-economic conditions require such qualities as entrepreneurship, politeness, readiness to adapt to new working conditions from graduates of technical institutes. A production specialist has to deal with an abundant flow of information that needs to be properly received, processed and communicated, which is impossible without personal communication resources.

According to a number of researchers, students of the technical institute are distinguished by the development of non-verbal intelligence, which includes constructive activity skills, more developed spatial representations, a combination of formal logical thinking, synthetic and analytical thinking (L.A.Baranova, L.N.Borisova, V.N.Druzhinin, L.N.Sobchik). A high level of concentration, switching of attention, visual memory, high speed and accuracy of mental operations were found. Among the students of technical institutes, researchers note in the educational process the introversion of the individual, the dominance of knowledge motivation, the desire for independence, the lack of desire to rule, conscientiousness, responsibility, low level of emotion in communication with students, critical attitude to the environment.

For a student of the institute, the development of mental abilities becomes an important stage of professional formation: the ability to think theoretically, to abstract, to generalize is significantly developed. Qualitative changes in cognitive abilities: a non-standard approach to already known problems; the ability to introduce specific problems into general problems; ability to ask effective general questions even on the most poorly designed tasks.

However, the works of Z.I.Kalmikova [8], N.S.Leyts [9], B.M.Teplov [10] and others show that cognitive activity does not become sufficient activity without special complex effects, learning ability, thinking efficiency and student claims level decreases. The underdevelopment of cognitive activity is definitely compensated to one degree or another. If we proceed from the results of many studies, such compensation, first of all, hinders the development of the student's personality, which in turn leads to a decrease in cognitive activity or its one-sided development.

SUMMARY

In our opinion, cognitive activity includes a wide range of tasks. It can be an integral part of various academic and extracurricular activities of students, which helps to deepen and expand the scope of knowledge of the chosen specialty of the students. We are mainly based on the need to develop the student's creative qualities, needs and opportunities to go beyond the studied material, self-development and continuous self-education.

In general, cognitive activity, which serves as the most important factor of student development, is characterized by the need to expand the general horizon and increase the intellectual level.

Thus, only taking into account the age characteristics of students, we can effectively develop their cognitive activity. The latter is one of the leading mechanisms that ensure a high level of independence and responsibility of the student in the future.

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